

RepSEO Classifier

This is the official repository for our IEEE/ACM ICSE'25 [paper](#):

Mengying Wu, Geng Hong, Wuyuao Mai, Xinyi Wu, Lei Zhang, Yingyuan Pu, Huajun Chai, Lingyun Ying, Haixin Duan, Min Yang. *Exposing the Hidden Layer: Software Repositories in the Service of SEO Manipulation*. IEEE/ACM ICSE'25

Blackhat Search Engine Optimization through REPositories (RepSEO) is a novel attack vector where attackers carefully craft packages to manipulate search engine results, exploiting the credibility of software repositories to promote illicit websites.

RepSEO Classifier is the tool to detected those abusive packages in npm, Nuget, Docker Hub.

The attackers and our classifier focus on the **homepage** of packages, which are indexed by search engines. Thus, RepSEO packages often conspicuously display promotional content, which is typically illicit and **distinct** from other packages in the same software repositories. As promotion links are the core of SEO, the classifier also focuses on the **usage of links**, especially short links and unpopular links. Furthermore, attackers may upload multiple RepSEO packages using a single account considering **registration costs**, thus we consider historical behavior. We also model a benign package from their rich structure and metadata.

In sum, the classifiers include features from five aspects: structure, semantics, links, metadata, and historical behavior. The summary of features is shown below. The complete feature definition and details of feature engineering can be found in [Appendix_of_RepSEO.pdf](#).

Type	Feature	Data Type	Length
Structure	# of directories	int	1
	Presence of introduction	boolean	1
	Usage of HTML formatting	boolean	1
	Presence of code blocks	boolean	1
Semantic	Platform semantic distances	float	10
Link	Ratio of internal links	float	1
	Domain diversity of external links	int	1
	Ratio of short links	float	1
	Avg. rank of external domains	float	1
	Duplication of links	int	1
Metadata	Copyright license	boolean	1
	Official artifact	boolean	1
	Repository URL	boolean	1

Type	Feature	Data Type	Length
	Homepage URL	boolean	1
	Domain rank of homepage URL	float	1
	# of Download	int	1
Historical	User historical behavior	float	25

Setup

Base environment requirement:

- Linux
- python: 3.8
- 10GB or more of disk space

Download our artifacts by:

```
git clone https://github.com/Marphownio/RepSEO_Classifier.git
cd ./RepSEO_Classifier
```

Step 1. Prepare Docker Environment

To avoid any impact on the host machine from the code execution, it is recommended to use our artifacts in Docker container. Before building the image, please ensure that docker-related dependencies are installed on your computer.

Build docker image.

```
docker build -t repseo_classifier .
```

Then enter docker container.

```
docker run -it --name repseo repseo_classifier bash -c "cd
/RepSEO_Classifier && bash"
```

Please note that the following steps will all be executed inside the docker container.

Step 2. Apply for Translate API (*Optional*)

Translate API is needed to help **RepSEO** classifier better understand the semantic context of packages. You can choose to apply for one of the following translate API.

- Google Translate. Click [here](#) and get Google Cloud's **Access token** and **Project number or id**.
- Baidu Translate. Click [here](#) and get Baidu's **AppID** and **Key**.

Usage

RepSEO classifier consists of 3 sub-classifiers respectively for npm, NuGet and Docker Hub, all of which are of the same usage. We have prepared relevant test cases as input for the classifier. Each test case includes the metadata from the packages as well as their source files. For each repository, 25 abusive packages and 25 non-abusive packages are prepared and saved in their respective directories.

- `./RepSEO-classifier-npm/test_case/`
- `./RepSEO-classifier-nuget/test_case/`
- `./RepSEO-classifier-docker/test_case/`

The output of the classifier is the classification result for all test cases, and each test case will be labeled as **abuse** or **non-abuse**. Since the usage for all classifiers is the same, here we take the classifier for npm as an example.

Change to subdirectory of npm *RepSEO* classifier.

```
cd ./RepSEO-classifier-npm/
```

Export environment variables for translate API (*Optional*). Skip this step if you do not apply for any translation API.

```
# If you chose Baidu for translation
export BAIDU_APPID=<Your AppID of Baidu Translate API>
export BAIDU_KEY=<Your Key of Baidu Translate API>

# If you chose Google Cloud for translation
export GOOGLE_ACCESS_TOKEN=<Your Access Token of Google Cloud Translate API>
export PROJECT_NUMBER_OR_ID=<Your Number or ID of Google Cloud Translate API Project>
```

Run the *RepSEO* classifier.

```
python3 classify.py
```

Please note that the classification process may take some time. Specifically, loading the word2vec model takes approximately 5 minutes, and classifying each package requires around 0.8 seconds. For the provided test case of 50 packages, the total runtime is approximately 6 minutes. Please note that the actual execution time may vary depending on the hardware and software environment.

	Loading Word2Vec Model	Package Processing Rate
Expected Time	5 minutes	0.8 seconds per package

Result

The results generated by all three classifiers are saved in their respective directories as a csv file.

```
./RepSEO-classifier-npm/result/result_<time_stamp>.csv
./RepSEO-classifier-nuget/result/result_<time_stamp>.csv
./RepSEO-classifier-docker/result/result_<time_stamp>.csv
```

The csv files are saved in the format like

```
name, label, pred
<package_name>, <package_label>, <predication_by_classifier>
```

Data

Abusive Packages List

After conducting detection on the entire dataset, our tool discovered a total of 3,801,682 **RepSEO** packages in npm, NuGet, Docker Hub. Details are listed in the following directories respectively. To meet the file size limitation, the CSV file is split into multiple sub chunks.

```
./RepSEO-package-list/npm/
./RepSEO-package-list/nuget/
./RepSEO-package-list/docker/
```

Project Structure

```
├── README.md
├── RepSEO.pdf
├── Appendix_of_RepSEO.pdf
├── download_word2vec_model.sh           # File to download word2vec_model
├── download_tranco_list.py            # File to download domain rank file
├── download_nltk_model.py             # File to nltk related configuration
├── Dockerfile                          # File to setup docker environment
├── RepSEO-package-list                 # Lists of all detected abusive
packages
│   ├── npm
│   │   ├── .....
│   │   └── nuget
│   │       ├── .....
│   │       └── docker
│   │           ├── .....
├── RepSEO-classifier-npm              # Files of npm classifier
│   ├── .....
├── RepSEO-classifier-nuget            # Files of NuGet classifier
```


`file_extractor.py` to change the package extraction method. Fewer code modifications are sufficient to ensure a smooth adaption to other platforms.

Citation

If you find our work helpful, we would greatly appreciate it if you could cite our paper using the following BibTeX format.

```
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  author    = {Mengying Wu and Geng Hong and Wuyyao Mai and Xinyi Wu and  
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